

A Multifaceted Simulator Based on Intelligent System Logic Design

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Abstract

The system is a multi-operational logic unit with multiple access that includes differential equation and integrator controls, a user-friendly liable tool with combination of logic functions and controls using a 3D design module. It is capable of performing a set of arithmetic operations and a set of logical operations. The arithmetic and logic unit (ALU) is used as default and has been developed by a sequence of operations that activates a successful ALU design that follows (3) main modules (1) initialise study of existing ALU design and implementation (2) analyse and design for the proposed intelligent system (3) implementation of a desirable design of ALU as a default sample.

Keywords: Arithmetic and Logic Design, Intelligent system, 3D design module, System Combination, 2-bit ALU, Simulation phase, True table

Contribution and Purpose of Research

The main contribution and purpose of the paper is that the logic design procedure has several selected lines to select a particular operation in the unit. Many data inputs from one of its controls are combined with other inputs with the same input pins as the initial one to generate an operation at a particular point. The mode selection for an input distinguishes it between arithmetic and logic operation. The functions in the controls select inputs and specify a particular arithmetic or logic operation to be granted on the plot area. The user interface designed for the system allows for the system to be stopped and started and enables gain parameters at any initial state to be tuned. The model is in its initial stage and only worked as a closed loop that allows the logic configuration to be open for use and run in simulation mode as a generic real-time executable model.

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0.1 Introduction

Intelligent systems for logic designs is an intelligent tool that supports user-friendly and educational purposes, it provides easy access to logic designs and integrated system block model architecture (Rose et al. [13], Tatas et al. [15], Shafique et al. [14], Zhu et al. [20], Akopyan et al. [3]). In this paper, the initial stage of the system works by creating a simple user interface for the running and simulator model by displaying the system behaviour of the model in the graphic user interface (Lipp et al. [11], Yang et al. [18], Khamaj and Ali [9], Wang et al. [17], Brusilovsky et al. [5]). As a default, the user interface works with an exemplary model of a 2-bit ALU to test the design and graphic configuration of the system. Each gain block contains three continuous functions that integrate a gain function for the model to run. This procedure is derived from an advanced machine scheme that implements 3D modules on visual aesthetics and ergonomic attributes for engineering personnel (Irawan et al. [7], Kermavnar et al. [8], Kuo and Chu [10], Nayak [12], Fiorentino et al. [6]). Before discussing the mechanism behind its implementation a brief discussion of the literature is presented.

The concept behind intelligent systems is that they are technologically advanced machines that are for perceiving and responding to the world around us through complex phenomena more user friendly and approachable. These intelligent systems are in many forms include automated vacuums, the main area within its environment is how machines perceive their surroundings and they interact with the environment. One of the well-known ways where such a system can perceive its environment is through a vision in the visual interface. Intelligent systems such as the once for control system and logic design which are often known as simulators (Truemper [16], Albus et al. [4], Abraham and Nath [2], Zadeh [19], Abraham [1]) are usually rare and complex to design. Some are made to use add and drop controls or simply drag and draw without initial parameter entries for the simulation. Parameters such as the gain function will always need a placeholder for every logic design and intelligent systems of this kind need to be straightforward and user friendly to contain control blocks for gain and gain placeholders. Research on intelligent systems of logic design faces numerous challenges some of these challenges include dynamic physical world simulation, such as uncertainty, time-consuming computation, maximum simulation time estimate and mappings.

0.2 Method

The user interface designed for the system allows for the system to be stopped and started and enables gain parameters at any initial state to be tuned. The model is in its

initial stage and only works as a closed loop that allows the logic configuration to be open for use and run in simulation mode as a generic real-time executable model. In simulated modality, the input parameters for the signal behaviour are fed to the gain block and the signal is displayed in the scope axes. The external mode only allows for data entries from a specific type of block such as the scope block. An index window is first created when the system is activated at the initial stage (Figure 0.1). This gives information about the system license and how to use it as form documentation and procedure steps. A new project is set up anytime the "create new project" button is activated.

The default logic design used for the system is a two-bit ALU (Figure 0.2) where the boxes are on the right-hand side of the control blocks and consist of multiplexers which are to select between different operations such as OR, AND, XOR, and addition gates. All operations are performed in parallel and selected signal blocks are used to determine which result in a set as attributes to pass on the data path. The carry signal is used for addition and it is generated and passed out to the proceeding ALU for every operation, if addition is performed, then the process is ignored and treated as a carry flag.

The rationale for using a 3D ALU system design is that it integrates and stacks multiple boards on top of each other's weight with a particularly dense board-to-board interface. It enables the circuit design capable of replacing long wires with short vertical interconnections in the design view thereby reducing delay in related wire and power consumption and simulation speed. This paper evaluates a default logic design of a 3D prototypical intelligent system of ALU and its functional units. The adders are discussed briefly in (Tatas et al. [15]), and the shifters have very different delay characteristics. The adder's critical path is dominated by logic gate delays and gains. Here we demonstrate the potential benefit of a 3D ALU system, which specifies latency at the simulation phase which exhibits a 0.07% reduction latency and a maximum simulation speed of 0.001sec/sec.

0.3 Result

The multiplexer control blocks designed have had a combinational circuit with a maximum of 2^n data inputs, ' n ' selection lines, and a single output line. Each data input is connected to the output based on the values of the selection line. With n selected lines, there will be a 2^n possible combinations of zeros and ones. Each combination will select only one data input. Each control block in the window interface (Figure 3) is activated by selecting a desirable control in drag and drop form that links each block to the other. This form is easy and user-friendly, when each connection is matched properly for a digital circuit design

Figure 1: Index frame of the Logic simulator with system intro.

Figure 2: A 3D 2-bit ALU design from the intelligent system.

and one can easily run the simulation, the result from the combination is the truth table configuration of the system (Figure 4), and the setup is obtained from the following Boolean function as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= D4 + D5 + D6 + D7 \\
 B &= D2 + D3 + D6 + D7 \\
 C &= D1 + D3 + D5 + D7
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{0.1}$$

The window interface (Figure 5) includes the controls

Figure 3: User Interface for the Intelligent Logic System.

The image shows a 'TruthTable' window from the simulator. It contains a table with the following data:

		Inputs					
		D0	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5
Inputs	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Outputs	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 4: The Truth Table from the system configuration in the digital logic simulator.

for gain parameter input, the name of the newly configured logic circuit, and the simulation mode i.e. this is either based on real-time simulation or optimized for fixed and floating-point (GRT), this automatically updates active configuration parameters of the parent model for a fixed or

floating-point code generation. The Scope block displays the input and signal behaviour of the time. For this case, the default model is not continuous but we introduced a trig function for each input logic gate with the following scheme:

Figure 5: Windows interface for scope and controls for system configuration signal behaviour.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N N \sin x + N \cos(x) = y \quad (0.2)$$

Where x is the input for each logic gate between 1 to N number of logic gates (*OR* and *AND* gates) depending on the form of system configuration. Y is the resultant output from the input entries shown in Figure 5, which relays the system behaviour. The scope allows for the adjustment of time and the range of input values displayed. It can also be moved and resized by adjusting the window borders and can be modified by changing its input parameters during simulation. When displaying a vector or matrix signal, the scope assigns different colors to each signal output. The scope displays the output of the default model, the simulation is run for less than 40 seconds and can also be adjusted to a lesser time frame. The time offset field displays the time corresponding to 0 on the time axes that can be used for other continuous system configurations. One of the system's drawbacks is the flexibility and design module given to each control block, very few of the blocks lack a driven control module and this will be adjusted with subsequent versions.

0.4 Conclusion

This paper set out to design a 3D complex simulator for an intelligent system for deep logic design. The system uses a multi-operational logic unit with multiple access

that includes differential equation and integrator controls, it allows the user to have access to a liable tool with combination logic functions and controls using a 3D design module. The system is capable of performing a set of arithmetic operations and a set of logical operations. The design module allows the logic controls to have access to several selected lines to select a particular operation in the unit. Some data inputs from one of its controls are combined with other inputs with the same input pins as the initial one to generate an operation at a particular point. The mode selection for an input distinguishes it between arithmetic and logic operation. The functions in the controls select inputs and specify a particular arithmetic or logic operation to be granted on the plot area. One of its drawbacks is its inability to insert design controls on the other logical blocks and this is one of our future perspectives, to insert design modules in all control blocks for a standalone system that would be useful in education course level in design and simulation of electrical and mathematical models.

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